

**DESEMNARE, SEMNIFICAȚIE, SENS – APLICAREA CONCEPTELOR
DIN TEORIA LUI EUGEN COȘERIU ÎN STUDIAREA MANIEREI
DE TRADUCERE A DOUĂ CRONOGRAFE DIN SECOLUL AL XVII-LEA:
„HRONOGRAF DEN ÎNCEPUTUL LUMII”, DE NICOLAE MILESCU
SPĂTARUL ȘI „NOVĂ ADUNARE DI ISTORII”,
DE MITROPOLITUL DOSOFTEI AL MOLDOVEI (I) /**

**DESIGNATION, SIGNIFICATION, MEANING – APPLYING
EUGEN COȘERIU’S THEORETICAL CONCEPTS TO THE STUDY
OF TRANSLATION METHODS IN TWO 17th-CENTURY CHRONOGRAPHS:
„HRONOGRAF DEN ÎNCEPUTUL LUMII” (*HRONOGRAF FROM THE BE-
GINNING OF THE WORLD*) BY NICOLAE MILESCU SPĂTARUL
AND „NOVĂ ADUNARE DI ISTORII” (*NEW COLLECTION OF HISTORIES*)
BY METROPOLITAN DOSOFTEI OF MOLDAVIA (PART I)**

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The old literary Romanian language was to a large extent the result of constant literal practice applied to translations, rendered in one of the old literary Romanian dialects. Among the texts that were translated in old times, a number of them did not observe this tendency and revealed a specific detachment from the original text. The transla-

tions of the chronographs, for instance, provided a good example as autonomous literary genres, both in the universal and the Romanian literature. One such example is *The Chronograph from the Beginning of the World* (ms. 3517 BAR) that was translated, according to our sources, by a Moldavian scholar, Nicolae Milescu Spătarul, between 1658-1661, using two old Greek chronographs, that of Mattheos Kigalas *Νεῖα σύνοψις διαφορῶν ἱστοριῶν ἀρχομένη ἀπό κτίσεως κόσμου...*, and certain paragraphs from Dorotheos of Monemvasia's *Βιβλίον ἱστορικὸν περιέχον ἐν συνόψει διαφόρους καὶ ἐξόχους ἱστορίας ...* as well as other texts. Three decades later, between 1686–1693, while in exile in Poland, Metropolitan Dosoftei of Moldavia, another remarkable figure of the old Romanian culture, translated Mattheos Kigalas' chronograph, using the unique original entitled *New Collection of Histories...* (ms. 3456 BAR). To approach the translation methods applied to both Romanian versions, we rely on the theoretical differences advanced by Eugen Coșeriu, based on three concepts: *designation*, *significance* and *sense*. A comparative approach starting from Matheos Kigalas' original Greek text reveals two different methods of microtext translation, that of Nicolae Milescu's more autonomous translation as compared to the original Greek text and that of Metropolitan Dosoftei's, whose tendency was toward designation, but more literally-prone than the former.